

A Study on Absenteeism at Shri Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt.Ltd, Dindigul

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ABSTRACT

The study is about absenteeism in Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt. Ltd. The study was carried out in Dindigul for the period of 8 weeks. The aim of the study was to find the level of absenteeism and the reason for absenteeism in Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt. Ltd. Primary data were collected using self constructed questionnaire comprising of 16 questions which were framed using Likert's 5 point scale. Secondary data were collected using journals, books, magazine and online portal. Population of the study was 150 workers and sample size of the study was 110 workers. Samples were selected using simple random sampling technique. Statistical tools such as chi - square, and ANOVA were used for analysis. Reports were prepared in American Psychological Association (APA) style. It was found that the level of absenteeism was moderate and the reason for absenteeism was lack of enough holidays.

KEYWORDS: Absenteeism, workers, Remuneration, Lack of holidays

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I. INTRODUCTION

Simple absenteeism implies an employee's inability to report on duty when scheduled to work. When the employer has job accessible to him and the worker is conscious of it, an employee is regarded to be scheduled to work. An employee shall be regarded as absent for the purpose of statistics on absenteeism even if, after receiving previous authorization, he does not appear for job.

If even for part of the day or shift an employee reports for duty, he cannot be counted among absentees. Lack of an worker due to strike or local-out or layoff, which is involuntary absence, will not fall within the scope of term absenteeism.

The rate of absenteeism is measured by applying the formula

$$\frac{\text{Man - days lost due absence}}{\text{Man - days schedule to work}} \times 100$$

Frequent employee lack impacts the smooth work flow in the organization and man's loss-days lead to loss of production. Because of a shortage of manpower, the companies will not be able to achieve their manufacturing goal. If it does not achieve its manufacturing goal, it will also become hard to achieve the sales goal. Failure to achieve sales target outcomes in the company failing to achieve its intended profit level. High absenteeism rate results in idle plant capability. This is because the lack of the necessary

manpower outcomes in the machine capability being used. The company may sometimes have to appoint temporary or casual workers instead of the missing-staff. The quality of the job performed is impacted because the casual employees may not be as effective as the concern's periodic employees. The company will not be able to carry out its customers' orders quickly due to absence of manpower.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Absenteeism, in simple terms, means the failure of an employee to report for duty when he is scheduled to work. An employee is considered as scheduled to work when the employer has work available for him and the employee is aware of it. An employee is to be treated as absent for the purpose of absenteeism statistics even when he does not turn up for work after obtaining prior permission. The factors influencing the absenteeism,

NATURE OF JOB

If the nature of job performed by the employee is dull and monotonous, he is likely to be absent frequently. This happens because, the employees loses interest in work. He feels physically and mentally tired.

HEALTH GROUND

For health reasons, an employee may be absent for work frequently. If the employee or anybody in his family falls sick often, he may not be able to be regular for work.

PERSONAL WORK

An employee, sometimes, may have to attend to some personal work for the sake of which he may be absent for work. Such a need may arise when an employee, building a house, has to supervise construction work or is on a pilgrimage tour and so on.

STRESS CONDITION

Another important reason for absenteeism is that many workers undergo stress. Such stress conditions develop due to domestic commitments and work pressure. Many individuals lack the mental courage to handle crises. This affects their mental health.

UNATTAINABLE TARGETS

Some employees set targets that are beyond the reach of their employees. This may force some employees to proceed on leave frequently.

LACK OF HOLIDAYS

In some organisations, the employees may not be given holidays even on certain important festival days. This forces them to be absent for work on such days.

SOCIAL COMPULSIONS

Every person has certain social compulsions. A marriage in a person's family, for example, forces him to avail leave to make the necessary arrangements. Same things happen when a job search process. Employees will not be quick to volunteer information that they are seeking employment elsewhere, and most will not consider resignation until another position has been secured. However, there are some obvious signs that can help alert employers to unhappy employees seeking greener pastures. Is an employee demonstrating a noticeable change in attitude, with less communication to management? Are they taking longer lunch breaks and an abundance of personal phone calls? Are they showing up at the office dressed to the nines with portfolio in hand? If these factors are causing increased rates of absence, action must be taken to find the root of the issue and convince the employee to stay on board (Robert Half, 2015). death occurs in a family (Dr. J. Jayasankar in 2016).

ABSENTEEISM

The aim of this study was to investigate the impact of absenteeism and the extent to which it negatively affects organizational performance. The study focused to understand negative result of absenteeism in the workplace and extensively seek to provide insight into the causes of absenteeism. The researcher has also suggested the strategies to be deployed by management for reducing the absenteeism and promote attendance in the workplace (Tamara Singh Et.al in 2016).

This paper has focused on absenteeism as a major obstacle for retail sector and how it gives the increase effect on organization growth and development. In this study the researcher has identified the impact and causes of absenteeism among employees in Retail Shops. This study ensures that the organizational performance brings good result during the complete presence of employee (Habeebur Rahman in 2016).

Absenteeism is one of the ever present problems of the pharmaceutical industry. In this study the various causative

factors leading to absenteeism in pharmaceutical Industry is analysed critically. The absenteeism factors includes social such as alcoholism, family conflict, lack of proper motivation, working problems, health problem, transport problems, religious and age factor etc. (Dr. Abhinav Patel, Sanjay Thakkar in 2014).

This study aims to identify factors that result in employees' absenteeism in an organization, which may help the company manager to develop and identify attitudes of employees for minimizing absenteeism. The results indicated the necessity feedback on employee's performance. A good interpersonal relationship for the smooth functioning of the organizational activities should be maintained. High rates of employee absence may signal weak labour management relations and low productivity (M. Prabhu in 2013).

This study was conducted in concern to identify the issues, causative and remedial measures related to absenteeism. This research helps the organization to know their current practices regarding for reducing absenteeism in Titan Industry. It suggested the measures to improve the business in better prospect and result in organizational development by reducing employee absenteeism (Dr. Renuka Rathod, Mr. Basavanth Reddy in 2012).

The success of organization in terms of profitability, efficiency, growth depends on the contribution of employee towards objective. The rate of absenteeism can be reduced with mutual commitment and involvement of employer and employee. The provision of various welfare facilities, work culture, communication, training, HR Policies can reduce absenteeism to involve substantial financial commitment for the management. Hence, absenteeism is invisible and unpredictable in nature that proves fatal for the industry (Harish K. Padmanabhan in 2017).

The least expensive and best practice for significantly lowering unnecessary employee absences is to implement systems of positive reinforcement, flexible scheduling, and disciplinary proceedings to deal with excessive absences. At any rate, solving company absence issues will allow employers to receive greater employee efficiency and lower the costs of losing out on that extra day of work and increase company productivity and profitability (Mehmet C. Kocakülâh, Stevie Lynch & Timothy G. Bryan in 2018).

When an employee is absent from work, this can have a number of generic effects on company output. While the only disadvantages to the employee of not returning to work are possible loss of pay and disciplinary actions, the coworker will immediately bare a large portion of the responsibility for the absence. Coworkers will be saddled with a large amount of work to keep up with the loss in company productivity, and this may lead to an increase in overtime and the cost that comes with it. The company may also experience an increase in accidents that could occur due to coworkers being confronted with unfamiliar machines or sets of job activities. This increase of labor for coworkers will affect the entire work group. Coordination problems will reach a climax, and productivity may decline if the replacement worker is less skilled than the absent worker (Atkin & Goodman in 1984).

Small steps can be taken along the way to prevent the spread of diseases throughout the workplace as well. Hand washing is the most effective way to prevent the spread of communicable disease, and elementary schools have recently begun to recognize the benefits of including alcohol-free instant hand sanitizer throughout classrooms. A recent study revealed that after just 5 weeks, students using the active product were 33% less likely to have been absent because of illness (White in 2014).

A number of methods have been put into place in order to possibly find a cure for absenteeism related to illness. The most popular of these methods is to require proof of illness by employees. However, the extent to which an employer may inquire into the nature of and reasons for an employee's absence from the workplace is a delicate issue. The concepts of an employee's privacy and an employer's need for information affecting the workplace often come into conflict. In addition, unions will often strongly object to any efforts by management to inquire more deeply into the nature of an employee's illness (Benefits Interface in 2014).

The issue of employees absenteeism and explores in detail preventative and corrective actions absenteeism has a negative impact on a company's employees morale. To reduce employee absenteeism there were different types of programs were implemented, absenteeism is calculated by using various rates such as absenteeism rate, Frequency rate, and severity rate. Through there are limitations the person department is taking special care to frame certain policies and procedures that reduce absenteeism and increase the labor turn over. Majority of workers is facing problems in 1st shift the company has to take necessary steps to reduce the problems. Most of the workers do not intimate their senior regarding their leaves this is another reason for employee absenteeism (S. Salomy, D. Ankitha & V. Divya in 2017).

VI. Analysis and Interpretation

Chart 1 showing levels of absenteeism

Level of absenteeism at Shri Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt. Ltd. Is found to be at moderate level as the average 53.3 lies between 37.6 to 59.2 which is moderate

Table 1 showing analysis using chi - square

ABSENTEEISM \ REMUNERATION	OCCATIONALLY ABSENT	FREQUENTLY ABSENT	TOTAL
POSTIVE REMUNERATION	25	40	65
NEGATIVE REMUNERATION	20	25	45
TOTAL	45	65	110

Source: Primary Data

Chi - Square: 0.394
 Degrees of freedom: 1
 P - value: 0.5

III. Objective of the study

1. To find the level of absenteeism at Shri Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt. Ltd.
2. To find whether absenteeism is influenced by remuneration.
3. To find whether absenteeism is influenced by benefits and welfare measures provided by the organisation.

IV. Hypotheses of the study

Null hypothesis

1. Absenteeism is not influenced by remuneration.
2. A) There is no significant difference in the level of absenteeism for different age group of employees .
 B) There is no significant difference in the level of absenteeism for male and female employees.

V. Research Methodology

A sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population. It refers to the technique or the procedure the researcher would adopt in selecting items for the sample. This study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected using questionnaire. Scaling technique used for the study is Likert 5 point scale. The scale comprises of strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree. Absenteeism score of 16 to 37.6 is consider as low absenteeism score, values from 37.7 to 59.2 are consider as moderate absenteeism score and values 59.3 to 80 are consider high absenteeism. In this study simple random sampling is used to collect data. There the sample of 110 workers has been selected for the study from the population of 150. The statistical tools such as chi - square and ANOVA is used for analyzing the impact of absenteeism at Shri Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt. Ltd. at Dindigul.

The above table 1 shows that the value of chi - square is 0.394 and P - value is 0.5 which is greater than 0.05. Hence we accept the null hypotheses. Therefore it was inferred that absenteeism is not influenced by remuneration.

Table 2 showing absenteeism score of workers with various age group

AGE	NO.OF WORKERS	Percentage	AVG. absenteeism	Level of Absenteeism
20 - 30 yrs	24	22	54	Moderate
31 - 40 yrs	33	30	53.3	Moderate
41 - 50 yrs	32	29	53	Moderate
51 yrs & above	21	19	52.6	Moderate
	110	100		

Source: Primary Data

The above table 2 shows that 30% of the workers are under the age of 31 - 40 years and the level of absenteeism is moderate. 29% of them are under age group of 41 - 50 years and the level of absenteeism is moderate. 22% of workers are under the age group of 20 - 30 years and the level of absenteeism is moderate. 19% are under the age group of 51 years & above the level of absenteeism is moderate.

Table 3 showing absenteeism score of workers with male & female

OPINION	Respondent	Percentage	AVG. absenteeism	level of Absenteeism
Male	60	55	53.27	Moderate
Female	50	45	53.42	Moderate
	110	100		

Source: Primary Data

The above table 3 shows that majority of 55% of workers are male workers and level of absenteeism is moderate were as 45 % of workers are female workers in Shri Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt. Ltd. and the level of absenteeism is moderate.

Table 4 showing difference in the level of absenteeism for different age group of employees .

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
20 - 30 YEARS	25	1296	54	29.043
31 - 40 YEARS	33	1761	53.363	27.113
41 - 50 YEARS	32	1704	53.25	26.903
51 YEARS & ABOVE	20	1106	52.666	25.433

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	20.251	4	6.750	0.248	0.862	2.690
Within Groups	2878.3030	106	27.153802			
Total	2898.554545	110				

Source: Primary Data

The above table 4 shows that the calculated value of F 0.248 which is less than the table value of 2.690 at 5% level. Also p- value is greater than 0.05. hence this could have arisen due to chance. This analysis support the null-hypothesis of no difference in sample mean.

Table 5 showing difference in the level of absenteeism for male & female employees .

Anova: Single Factor

Summary

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
MALE	60	3196	53.267	7.758
FEMALE	50	2671	53.42	49.799

ANOVA

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.641212121	2	0.641212121	0.023896819	0.877436261	3.929011718
Within Groups	2897.913333	108	26.83253086			
Total	2898.554545	110				

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that the calculated value of F 0.0238 which is less than the table value of 3.9290 at 5% level . Also p- value is greater than 0.05. Hence this could have arisen due to chance. This analysis support the null-hypothesis of no difference in sample mean .

VII. Conclusion

Absenteeism refers to worker's absence from his regular work when he is normally scheduled to work. According to Labour Bureau, Simla defines "absenteeism as the failure of the worker to report for work when he is scheduled to work". The study has conducted at Shri Annalakshmi Spinning Pvt. Ltd. to find the level of absenteeism towards their workers. It was concluded that the level of absenteeism is moderate and there absenteeism is not influenced by remuneration.

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